

NGUYEN THANH TUAN
FINAL PROJECT

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FACULTY OF MECHANICAL ENGINEERING
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Developing advanced optimisation models for burnishing process

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FINAL PROJECT ASSIGNMENT

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Acceptance Statement

Master thesis title: Developing advanced optimisation models for burnishing process

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The master thesis mentioned above is fully compliant with all the content and formal requirements required by the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering of the Budapest University of Technology and Economics for the Diploma and Thesis assignments.

I consider this thesis to be suitable for review and public defence.

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Declaration of Independent Work

I, the undersigned, Nguyen Thanh Tuan (P8317F), student of the Budapest University of Technology and Economics, declare under my criminal and disciplinary responsibility, and with my own signature I certify that I have made this master thesis myself without any illicit help and I used only the specified resources. Any part that I have taken literally or in the same sense but reworded from other sources is clearly indicated by the provision of the source in accordance with the provisions in force.

Budapest, 2024

graduate student

A handwritten signature in blue ink, consisting of the letters 'Tuan' in a stylized, cursive script.

Nguyen Thanh Tuan

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1. Nomenclature

Abbreviations of terms

ANFIS	Adaptive network-based fuzzy inference system
ANN	Artificial neural networks
ANOVA	Analysis of variance
CIC	Circularity
CSA	Crow search Algorithm
CYL	Cylindricity
GRA	Gray relational analysis
GSO	Glowworm swarm optimization
LPB	Low plasticity burnishing
MAR	maximum profile peak height of roughness
MF	Membership functions
MOGSO	Multi-objective glowworm swarm optimization
MQL	Minimal quantity lubrication
MQLAMRB	Minimal quantity lubrication-assisted multi-roller burnishing
MSE	Mean square error
NSPSO	non- dominated sorting particle swarm optimization
NDM	Near-dry machining
PSO	Particle swarm optimization
RMSE	Root-mean-square error
TOPSIS	Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution
UHMWPE	Ultra High Molecular Weight Polyethylene
VCPSO	Vibration and communication particle swarm optimization

Units of quantities

Notation	Name, notes, value	unit
S	spindle speed	RPM
V_f	feed rate	mm/min
D	burnishing depth	mm
SR	surface roughness	μm
VH	Vickers hardness	HV
NE	number of experiments (NE)	
k	number of parameters	
C_p	number of center points	
\bar{X}_{mn}	Standardize the matrix	
(V^+)	Positive ideal solution	
(V^-)	Negative ideal solution	
w(n)	assigned weight	
D_m^+, D_m^-	Euclidean distance	
C_m	the closeness index	

2. Introduction

Super surface finish is a rising necessity in production sectors. Burnishing is a method of mechanical surface treatment that improves various material components' mechanical qualities and surface textures. It is both a beneficial procedure for obtaining exact surfaces and a surface treatment using a rigid spherical tool to apply workload and friction to restricted areas on a workpiece. More particularly, it causes the material to be plastically deformed and the existing defects to be flattened.

Despite helping to enhance the surface, burnishing still needed to be developed and the process parameters optimized to reach desired surface characteristics. Conventionally, optimization methods often relied on trial and error or poorly calibrated models, with factors not fully grasping the complex interactions between such factors and surface properties.

To overcome these issues, this research focuses on a novel approach to optimize the burnishing model. AI techniques, artificial intelligence, and multi-objective optimization methods are combined to explore the parameter space in a more organized way and find the best settings to perform the process. The model uses AI advances such as learning and neural networks to gain a measure of the data and predict the relationship between process parameters and surface quality indicators. Additionally, multi-objective optimization means that several competing goals can be evaluated concurrently, such as roughness and hardness. This project's goal is to optimize the burnishing technology using a novel approach to optimization. The model will offer producers a potent tool to optimize the parameters of the process and receive great finish characteristics. Insights and approaches acquired on the background of this project have great potential to impact production sectors' competitiveness.

3. Aim, objectives, and methodology

Burnishing is a procedure that is accomplished to boost the surface characteristics of metallic components that integrate the usage of a metal ball or roller. As a result, the efficiency and sturdiness of metal components can be enhanced for a wide range of applications in certain industries. In Burnishing, producing the optimum direct surface hardness and reducing the surface roughness to a minimum is critical because they have an impact on the mechanical and functional characteristics of the finished goods.

In connection to improving the burnishing technique with an effort to address the issue, this investigation recommends that a sophisticated optimization model be developed to produce a viable solution. This study seeks to apply the anticipatory power of Artificial Neural Networks and the Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) strategy in order to formulate an optimization model framework that is both high-performance and successful. With the optimization model, the Artificial Neural Networks will make extremely accurate surmises about surface hardness and surface roughness based on the provided input parameters, including spindle speed, feed rate, and tool burnishing depth. The subsequent TOPSIS methodology will place the solution alternatives in a hierarchy based on the provided ANN prediction model, in this case, both average surface hardness and surface roughness will be maximized and minimized in parallel. The purpose of this undertaking is to provide a broad and orderly optimization approach to improve the burnishing technique. The model created has the ability to enhance the quality and performance level of burnishing surfaces by changing the technique characteristics to match the wants of a specific application. As businesses that depend on burnishing transform, outcomes of the research are expected to benefit companies. Which include gains in product quality, effectiveness, and competitiveness.

4. Literature review

This chapter reviews in detail research on the overview of the burnishing process, the effect of burnishing parameters on surface properties, and the application of Artificial Intelligence to optimize the burnishing process.

4.1. Burnishing – An overview

4.1.1 Burnishing – The definition

Burnishing is a process that occurs after machining, where the workpiece undergoes plastic deformation at a layer less than a micron. This process modifies the surface of the component by exerting pressure on it with a precisely polished and hardened ball or roller design (Al-Bsharat, Hassan AM, 1996). The burnishing method achieves a mirror-like sheen by pressing down the peaks into the valleys, yet it does not remove any material from the surface (Hassan AM, Al-Bsharat AS, 1996).

As the balls circle the workpiece's surface, as shown in Figure 4.1, the material is compressed and forced into the low spots between the high ones. To burnish, one uses a moving tool with a freely rotating ball or roller. This process results in plastic deformation of the surface layers (Fattouh M, El-Axir MH, 1988).

Fig 4.1. Burnishing leads to the transformation of a surface (Ovali et al., 2011)

Plastic deformation is an advantageous process that only takes place in the sublayer of the workpiece material, which results in the smoothing of the uneven surface on a permanent basis.

Thus, the hardness of the burnishing tools needs to be strong enough in order to ensure the occurrence of plastic deformation. There are several types of the most widely used metal ball tool materials, such as bearing steel, silicon nitride ceramic, alumina carbide ceramic, and silicon carbide ceramic. The cemented carbide tool is the most functional one within the 40 to 100 N burnishing forces. The silicon nitride ceramic tool hardly burnishes compared to the cemented carbide tool. Furthermore, silicon carbide and alumina ceramic burnishers are not commonly used (Ahmed Raza, Sudhanshu Kumar, 2022).

Traditionally, machining methods such as turning, milling, and others produce surface flaws and intrinsic faults. These, in turn, result in friction and surface damage. As a result, the time of product life is shortened. Besides, the metallurgical qualities are removed, and the product quality is decreased. Grinding, honing, and lapping are examples of traditional superfinishing processes, which take away the flaws. Superfinishing processes are mandatory for obtaining the desirable finish of the surface. Challenging is, however, that it requires a person who worked with the technology, depending on several factors. The concerns mentioned in the cited work were successfully addressed by using the burnishing technique, which results in a better polish of the surface, but without the removal of the chip. Due to the topography of the surface to be created, the material's life is also determined. Thus, bearing in mind the inherent flaws, the traditional method should be rejected in favor of the post-machining process. (Ahmed Raza, Sudhanshu Kumar, 2022).

4.1.2 The benefit of the burnishing process

The burnishing method has been proven advantageous in enhancing the surface integrity of both soft and hard machined surfaces. Conventional abrasive processes consume a higher amount of power and can potentially result in surface damage. Burnishing is a procedure where a harsh, round-edged instrument is used to contact a work surface by rolling or sliding (El-Tayeb NSM et al., 2008).

When the tool makes contact with the workpiece surface, it exerts significant tension on the workpiece. The applied stress exceeds the material's yield strength, leading to plastic deformation extending to a few micrometers of depth. This deformation induces compression of the asperities. This process induces work hardening through the permanent plastic deformation, resulting in a consistently smooth and uniform surface texture (Low KO, Wong KJ, 2011).

Figure 4.2 depicts the spatial arrangement of stress levels throughout the burnishing process. When a force is applied to the burnishing tool, it compresses the component's material, leading to the formation of residual compressive stresses. The compressive stresses are highly enduring and remain during normal conditions (Ahmed Raza, Sudhanshu Kumar, 2022).

The burnishing process enhances material properties (Lee, 1993). These improvements can be utilized to decrease the resistance and sticking of surfaces throughout the burnishing procedure (El-Tayeb NSM et al., 1994). Moreover, it significantly enhances the characteristics of a substance by integrating surface hardness, microgeometric alteration, and the revelation of compressive stress through heterogeneous plastic deformation on the material's surface (Luo H et al., 2005) (Gharbi F et al., 2015). The conventional superfinishing process, known for generating undesirable tensile stress and reducing resistance to fatigue, can be substituted with the burnishing process. Burnishing converts tensile stress into compressive stress, resulting in positive effects on the material and improving the fatigue life of the component (Zhuang HG, WZ, 2001).

The burnishing process has several technological elements that provide advantages over the typical superfinishing technique in terms of (Ahmed Raza, Sudhanshu Kumar, 2022):

1. The surface and underlying layers experience enhanced compressive residual stress.
2. The procedure does not require lubrication, which enhances its specialization and environmental friendliness.
3. Chipless, meaning it saves material.
4. The procedure exhibits a high rate and efficiency.
5. The surface exhibits exceptional quality with minimal roughness and outstanding precision.
6. Ability to produce large quantities efficiently.
7. The machined surface is free of any abrasive particles.
8. Reduced heat generation on the machined surface.

While the burnishing process is considered superior to other traditional finishing methods by many people, it has several constraints. First, due to the cost of burnishing tools, it takes package designers and manufacturers a considerable initial investment to adopt burnishing. Second, it is challenging to burnish components with thin walls. Finally, it is difficult to burnish subtle curves and contours

effectively using the special equipment and highly skilled labour that must be applied to a burnishing operation (Ahmed Raza, Sudhanshu Kumar, 2022).

Figure 4.2. Illustration of the distribution of stress that occurs during the process of burnishing (Ahmed Raza, Sudhanshu Kumar, 2022).

4.1.3. Categorization of the burnishing process

a) Determined by the deforming element geometry

Based on the shape of the deforming element, burnishing machining can be categorized into ball burnishing and roller burnishing processes. The ball burnishing process utilizes a spherical deforming tool that is in point contact with the work materials. In addition, the ball that is in contact with the work material is usually much harder than the material. On the other hand, the roller burnishing process uses a cylindrical deforming element that is continuously in line contact with the work material.

On the other hand, the roller burnishing method results in a much superior tool surface interaction than the former. The roller used in the roller burnishing process must be highly hard as well as have excellent wear resistance properties. High carbon steel, carbon chromium, EN31 with Titanium Nitride coating, tungsten carbide and HSS steel are some common materials used to prepare the rollers most suitable for the roller burnishing process (Shankar E et al., 2008).

b) Determined by tool motion

The burnishing procedure can be executed using two distinct motions across the work surface: sliding and rolling. By sliding across the surface, the burnishing implement creates a sliding motion. The implement utilized in this particular burnishing process ought to possess a low coefficient of friction and a high resistance to abrasion. Diamond is superior to other materials utilized in this burnishing process, including ceramic, tungsten carbide, and high-alloy steel (Revankar GD et al., 2014).

Adhesion and seizures are considerably less frequent when rolling burnishing is utilized. Nevertheless, the tool device utilized in this burnishing procedure is exceedingly sophisticated, permitting the roller to rotate. The precision of the roller's rotation and operation influences the surface texture of the burnished material (S. C. T, Loh SMNH, 1989).

c) Determined by type of surface

Fig. 4.3. The Burnishing process is categorized by surface types (Ahmed Raza, Sudhanshu Kumar, 2022).

Figure 4.3 shows how the burnishing process is categorized by surface type: internal cylindrical (a), taper (b), contour (c), flat surface (d), and external (e). A multi-roller burnishing tool can be used to burnish the inside cylindrical surface. Rollers also burnish internal and external tapered surfaces.

The device frequently permits taper angle adjustment, allowing flat surfaces to be polished using milling-like techniques. The tool rotates around the vertical axis while the rollers spin parallel to the workpiece, improving its surface finish. Roller burnishing can be used to shape both concave and convex surfaces. However, the contour must remain symmetrical along the rotational axis, and any alterations can necessitate a new tool. The cylindrical exterior can be polished with either a ball or roller tool (Khalilpourazary S, Salehi J, 2019) (T. Nguyen and X. Le, 2018).

d) Determined by the design of tool burnishing

- Ball burnishing

Figure 4.4. The ball burnishing procedure

Figure 4.4 shows ball burnishing. The lathe machine chuck rotates, and the tail stock supports the burnishing surface to prevent bending. The burnishing tool consists of a removable adapter, a rigid spring, and a dial indicator. In the ball burnishing process, the vertical force, also known as the burnishing force, is of primary importance, whereas the other forces are relatively minor (Murthy BKRL, 1981). Helical springs create the burnishing force, which can be measured by a dial gauge, load cell, or dynamometer.

Burnishing is done with a tool with a hard ball. This ball is made of durable material. The ball's hardness is 69-80 HRC, with an average surface roughness of 0.003-0.176 μm . The ball

burnishing tool is commonly used to achieve dimensional tolerances below 0.01 (Lopez ' De Lacalle LN et al., 2005).

Ferrous materials like steel alloy undergo most ball burnishing (Shiou FJ et al., 2017). Non-ferrous metals like aluminum and brass can be ball burnished. Ball burnishing enhances the surface finish, hardness, fatigue strength, proof stress, and ultimate tensile strength by hardening the outer layer of the metal (Hassan AM, Al-Bsharat AS, 1996). More studies studied how shot peening and burnishing affect surface qualities (A.M. Hassan, A.M. S. Momani, 2000). Shot-peened components' roughness, hardness, fatigue strength, and corrosion resistance improve with burnishing. Ball burnishing on the lathe requires tool replacement. Three ball burnishing tools on a lathe's moveable rest are tested after changing three adjustable jaws. One or two balls cannot burnish as well as three balls (El-axir MH, Ibrahim AA., 2005).

Ball burnishing increases surface hardness and wear resistance. Burnishing convex and concave surfaces is also employed. The researcher found that ball burnishing increased the roughness of both concave and convex surfaces. The surface roughness was influenced by the curvature radius. Outstanding results were obtained with a small curvature radius on convex surfaces and a large curvature radius on concave surfaces (J.A. Travieso-Rodríguez et al., 2014).

- Roller burnishing

Roller burnishing produces a smooth surface finish by rolling hardened, polished rollers over machined surfaces. Roller burnishing is often used to polish elastic or ductile materials (John MRS, Vinayagam BK, 2016). The roller burnishing tool is useful for completing tapered holes, constantly curved surfaces, and inside and outside cylindrical surfaces (Al-Qawabeha UF, 2007).

Figure 4.5 shows roller burnishing. In roller burnishing, the contact region between the roller and work surface is initially a straight line (or point in ball burnishing), but gradually becomes a surface as the workpiece is moved along its length. Roller burnishing produces a better surface polish in less time than ball burnishing. The roller material should be robust and wear-resistant (Ahmed Raza, Sudhanshu Kumar, 2022).

Figure 4.5. Diagram illustrating the roller burnishing (Ahmed Raza, Sudhanshu Kumar, 2022)

- Low plasticity burnishing (LPB)

The low plasticity burnishing procedure (LPB) can also be referred to as the deep ball burnishing process (Rodríguez A et al., 2012). The burnishing tool is designed in a way that hydraulic pressure ensures constant contact between a rigid ball and the workpiece. The tool can accommodate various ball sizes, ranging from 8 to 20 mm in diameter. During this procedure, hydraulic fluid is supplied at a pressure of 40 MPa to exert pressure on the ball. The ball element exerts pressure on the surface of the component, causing the roughness peaks to become flattened. The ball is placed into a capsule and can rotate in any orientation.

Fig. 4.6. Principle of Hydrostatic ball burnishing (Ahmed Raza, Sudhanshu Kumar, 2022).

Figure 4.6 illustrates that the burnishing force is exerted utilizing hydraulic pressure, which is then transmitted to the work surface by a deforming device. During the sideways motion of the

burnishing tool, the material is subjected to pressure, leading to the formation of residual compressive stresses.

4.2. Literature review on the effect of burnishing parameter on surface properties

Tianze Li et al. have investigated the influence of burnishing pressure and route strategy on surface integrity and surface wettability of as-received Ultra High Molecular Weight Polyethylene (UHMWPE). It should be noted that the primary aim of the study was to determine the potential of the material to be used in anti-fouling applications. The results indicated that the burnishing provided a substantial decrease in the surface roughness of as-received UHMWPE. However, raising burnishing pressure over specific limits did not lead to any significant benefits in terms of roughness improvement. At the same time, the burnishing route pattern appeared to influence the outcomes greatly with the cross-path pattern being more advantageous than the single parallel one. Moreover, a surprising discovery is that high burnishing pressure yields an uneven surface topography and rippling texture. Such characteristics are beneficial for wettability as evident from the contact angles. The marine salt spray experiment indicated that the burnished surface has more water droplets sticking to it for an extended period, which leaves a hydration layer. These findings found further confirmation in fouling tests over 2 months, with the burnishing surface being less prone to fouling. The mechanism is related to strain hardening, with high burnishing pressure leading to greater surface hardness and a greater extent of permanent displacement of both amorphous and crystalline phases (Tianze Li et al., 2024).

Due to the combined influence of decreased roughness and enhanced hardness, burnishing significantly improved wear and impact resistance. In summary, the results indicate that applying the proper pressure and route approach during burnishing can boost the surface wettability and integrity of UHMWPE. This, in turn, leads to the formation of a mechanically stable hydration layer, which improves the antifouling performance of the material (Tianze Li et al., 2024).

According to the empirical findings of A. Nestler et al., applying slide diamond burnishing to AMCs causes a large reduction in average values of roughness and voids. Moreover, burnishing feed is a key factor that influences surface roughness. The burnishing force needs to be accurately determined to seal gaps within the burnished material to avoid material fatigue. Yet the process of sliding diamond burnishing applied to AMCs generates highly compressive residual stresses. The

findings of this study show that the residual stresses induced are close to compressive strength. The improved method enhanced the performance of components under vibrational loading. However, a more detailed assessment of residual stress distribution in the surface layer of the material is necessary (A. Nestler, A. Schubert, 2015).

Sachin B et al. examined the effect of diamond burnishing 17-4 PH stainless steel surface integrity with a new tool in a cryogenic, MQL, and dry environment. Surface finish in the cryogenic environment was superior being 33%–50%, 34–51%, and 25–40% greater than MQL and dry environments observed at all burnishing speeds, feed, and force. Surface hardness in the cryogenic environment was also better, being 5%, 6%, and 6% superior to MQL and 7%, 10%, and 9% better than dry. Subsurface microhardness was superior in the cryogenic environment by 7% and 9% to MQL and dry. Compressive residual stresses in the dry, cryogenic, and MQL envisaged were -215, 298, and -356 MPa. In sum, the innovative diamond burnishing tool improves the surface properties and subsurface properties in a cryogenic environment, increasing the potential of the product when compared to other burnishing environments. In conclusion, aircraft compressor blades and steam turbine engine parts should be burnished cryogenically as this process enhances surface integrity (Sachin B et al., 2019).

Researchers studied turning-burnishing surface modification in detail. The turning procedure produced the maximum surface roughness ($0.4947 \mu\text{m}$), which was greatly decreased by burnishing. After burnishing, the minimum surface roughness ($0.063 \mu\text{m}$) is 87.1% lower than after turning. The burnishing feed and number of passes significantly impact surface roughness. Additionally, the turning specimen surface shows alternate peaks and valleys. After burnishing, only small turning marks remain (Kunpeng Han et al., 2022).

The study conducted by Harish et al. relates to the significant effect of the ball and roller burnishing method on the general surface characteristic of the Al 2024 alloy. Roller and Hydrostatic Balls are stated to have a significant effect in general surface modification of Al 2024 Alloy when the right control of different parameters of the procedures is used. Roller burnishing application or treatment results in better surface roughness in comparison to the ball burnishing procedure. It also results in favorable compressive residual stress with reference to the ball burnishing method (Harish, D. Shivalingappa, 2020).

The study conducted by F. Gharbi et al. investigated the ball burnishing method on big flat plates constructed from AISI 1010 steel. According to the analysis of the experimental data involving the Taguchi approach and the response surface methodology, it follows that there is a possibility of obtaining an effective high-quality surface roughness in an acceptable period. The evaluation of the titanium alloy Ti6Al4V surfaces proves that burnishing power has the highest impact on the surface quality of AISI 1010 steel plates; after that, the burnishing speed is the factor that is the least influenced by the selected feed. In addition, the study allows the creation of a second order to predict the burnishing process's best parameters for AISI 1010 steel plates. It is recommended to use a burnishing speed of 235 RPM, a feed rate of 0.18 mm/rev, and a burnishing force of 400 N to obtain the best properties of the native burnished AISI 1010 steel plates' surface. Microstructure assessment proves that the applied force during the burnishing of AISI 1010 steel plates should not exceed 400 N because this action leads to the appearance of a metal flake. However, it is also paramount to note that if the force of burnishing increases, the depth of the hardened layer will also increase proportionally (Gharbi et al., 2011).

In 2018, Saldaña-Robles et al. demonstrated that ball-burnishing improved the average roughness and surface hardness of cylindrical bars produced by commercial AISI 1045 steel. The mean roughness indicator showed an 83% improvement in surface quality. A 14% increase in surface hardness from 202 to 236 HB was observed. A burnishing force of 294 N, feed rate of 0.2 mm/rev, and speed of 71 m/min significantly reduced Ra from 3.51 μm to 0.61 μm in the experimental research region. The statistical investigation showed that force and feed affect Ra more than speed. Additionally, decreasing feed rate and increasing force improve surface quality. The statistical study showed that just the burnishing force increased surface hardness. A mathematical equation with a 96% correlation coefficient was presented to characterize the experimental area's average roughness. This equation can reduce the number of experimental tests needed to attain the desired average roughness with an 8% error. The ideal burnished sample has a charge-transfer decrement and high resistance, indicating that burnishing improves corrosion resistance overturning (Saldana-robles et al., 2018).

4.3. The critical review of the application of artificial intelligence in the optimization of the burnishing process

The study conducted by An Le Van et. al focuses on optimizing the internal burnishing process using minimal quantity lubrication (MQL) to reduce the cylindricity (CYL) and circularity (CIC) of the burnished hole. The surface roughness (SR) is maintained within set limits as a constraint. The key factors for optimization are the spray nozzle diameter, the elevation angle of the spray, the quantity of lubricant, and the pressure of the compressed air. The proposed models of burnishing performances utilize artificial neural networks (ANNs) to optimize inputs. The grey relational analysis (GRA) is employed to calculate the weight value of each response. The vibration and communication particle swarm optimization (VCPSO) algorithm is used to identify the optimal values of MQL system characteristics and technological objectives (An Le Van, Trung Thanh Nguyen, 2022).

This study recommends using ANN, GRA, and VCPSO to handle complicated optimization problems and achieve optimal results. The presented approach has advantages such as minimal experimental costs, reduced human effort, and straightforward MATLAB software implementation. The optimization method is widely used to address optimization challenges in burnishing and other machining processes (An Le Van, Trung Thanh Nguyen, 2022).

Fig. 4.7. The structure for ANN models (An Le Van, Trung Thanh Nguyen, 2022)

MQL operation parameters (nozzle diameter, spray elevation angle, lubricant quantity, compressed air pressure) have been extensively analyzed for their effects on geometric deviations (cylindricity, circularity, and surface roughness). The acquired information aids machine operators in comprehending physical insights in the developed polishing procedure (An Le Van, Trung Thanh Nguyen, 2022).

The optimized results can improve machining performance. Results indicate that the MQL technology can improve internal hole machining quality in diverse components. Optimizing for cylindricity and circularity with a preset surface roughness restriction yields more realistic and consistent results than optimizing three objectives simultaneously. The study's findings can be used as valuable references for future research and expert systems on MQL-assisted internal polishing. The ANN models for CYL, CIC, and SR were substantial and accurate. Applying the proposed correlations can efficiently predict burnishing responses in industrial applications. The proposed ANN models can reduce experimental expenses and efforts (An Le Van, Trung Thanh Nguyen, 2022).

In order to use artificial intelligence for optimizing the process of ultrasonic burnishing, Reza Teimouri and others used it to predict the energy consumption for a certain surface roughness, arc height, and hardness. In this case, the process of optimization consisted of the combination of the adaptive network-based fuzzy inference system and particle swarm optimization. The concept of a fuzzy inference system based on adaptive networks is used to decide what to do in a correlated input-output connection. The supervised learning algorithms can control weighted functions that change according to the error of predictions. When it comes to fuzzy inference methods, the network itself generates weighted functions. The mentioned network has five layers: input, then fuzzification takes place and the models and membership functions are considered. There is also a rule layer for processing which, and the system gets the solution in the fourth layer: defuzzification. After that, the output is obtained in the last layer. For each response, one has to train and test ANFIS model building. Therefore, the first step is to gather data for developing an ANFIS network for a given reaction while training it. Then, in order to test the trained network, one uses more datasheets. Notes taken of a variety of fuzzy membership functions and learning algorithms are made during the training and testing, and the prediction error is calculated. The models were developed using MATLAB R17 ANFIS toolbox with Takagi-Sugeno network types. The most important MF type was

used in the models: triangular, trapezoid, modified bell with changing the number, RMSE was used to evaluate their performance. It is stated that the 3-3-3-3 ANFIS structure causes increasing the prediction error and the implementation time in comparison with the 2-2-2-2 ANFIS structure. Below are the values of forecast error for each MF type. The trapezoid MF can be predicted well by energy consumption, but triangular MF can be used to get various output responses. Then, one can consider Fig. 4.9, where the values of testing data that were expected by the ANFIS model are compared to the outcome of the experiment. It is clear to see that the experiment and measured values are very close. The established ANFIS model can be used for further analysis and finding the optimal result (Teimouri et al., 2019).

Fig. 4.8. ANFIS forecasts compared to measured values for energy, surface roughness, arc height, and hardness (Teimouri et al., 2019).

In the study of Minh Thai Le et al., the roller burnishing methods for hardened steel were enhanced, and the average roughness and Brinell hardness were reduced and improved by optimizing the spindle speed, feed rate, and penetration depth. The authors used Kriging to propose the correlational models of result metrics, and, in turn, they used Crow Search Algorithm (CSA) to determine the optimal results. These results are presented as follows: the increased speed and penetration may lead to an increase in the Brinell hardness. However, it is necessary to decrease the rate. The low speed and feed rate contributed to the smoother surfaces, while the high depth was recommended to be used. Also, the feed rate was determined to be the most critical factor related

to the surface's roughness. For all hardnesses, burnishing depth had the most significant reflections, whereas speed and feed rate followed. The optimization values of the speed, feed rate, and depth were calculated to be 832 RPM, 112 mm/ min, and 0.12 mm. The performance of the average roughness was enhanced by 29.9%, and Brinell Hardness improved by 37.0% (Le et al., 2023).

The minimum quantity lubrication-assisted multi-roller burnishing (MQLAMRB) operation was developed and optimized in Trung Thanh Nguyen et al.'s investigation to reduce total energy consumption (TE), mean roughness depth (MR), and roundness deviation (RN). The input factors included burnishing speed (BS), depth of penetration (DOP), lubricant quantity (QO), and compressed air pressure (PA) of the multi-roller burnishing process in sustainable lubrication conditions. To make interior hole machining easier, the MQL system and the MQLAMRB process operation principle have been suggested.

Fig. 4.9. An optimization strategy for the MQLAMRB system (Trung-Thanh Nguyen et al., 2022).

The MQLAMRB outputs were displayed using the ANN model. The glowworm swarm optimization (GSO) algorithm and the TOPSIS were used to help discover the best optimal point. It is challenging to choose the right operational parameters for the training ANN model. Seen on the right side of Fig. 4.9 is the suggested strategy for choosing the optimal ANN construction. The first step in this process is to choose the right number of concealed layers by carefully examining

published works. An orthogonal array matrix is used to help train the created artificial neural network (ANN) model with combinations of parameters. For each numerical trial, the PE value is computed and assessed. In this work, the optimal ANN model is selected by storing percentage errors less than 10%. The average mistake of three responses is taken into consideration if the lowest percentage of errors are comparable (Trung-Thanh Nguyen et al., 2022).

The glowworm swarm optimization (GSO) algorithm is used to choose the best results. The GSO is run according to how glowworms naturally behave at night. Every glowworm in the search space represents a feasible, ideal solution and has a specific indicator value, called luciferin. Lower luciferin particles will be drawn to higher ones. The glowworm with lesser luciferin, on the other hand, prefers to expand its local area in search of neighbors (Trung-Thanh Nguyen et al., 2022).

Trung Thanh Nguyen et al. optimized the internal roller burnishing technique to reduce surface roughness, machining noise, and energy consumption. Burnishing depends on roller count, depth, feed rate, and spindle speed. Using ANFIS, comprehensive models of technical performances are constructed for process parameters. Entropy was used to calculate burnishing target weights. The dominant sorting particle swarm optimization yielded the best results (Nguyen Trung Thanh et al., 2021).

Fig. 4.10. The 3-3-3-3 structure of the ANFIS model addresses the SR (Nguyen Trung Thanh et al., 2021).

The authors indicate that lower input levels reduce machining noise, whereas high burnishing parameter values boost energy efficiency. More rollers or burnishing depth reduce surface roughness, but a lower feed rate does. The intermediate spindle speed produces a smooth surface.

ANOVA shows that the energy efficiency, surface roughness, and machining noise ANFIS models are significant. Industrial burnishing responses can be predicted with considerable accuracy using these models. Internal roller burnishing on hardened SCr440 steel can be done using the provided models without costly experimentation. Based on the non-dominated sorting particle swarm optimization (NSPSO) -generated optimal configuration, the ideal spindle speed, feed rate, burnishing depth, and roller count are 1645 RPM, 260 mm/min, 0.08 mm, and 4. Surface roughness and machining noise decrease by 25.00% and 2.23%, respectively, while energy efficiency increases by 6.98%. The desired burnishing cost is 6.2% lower (Nguyen Trung Thanh et al., 2021).

The trial method and operator experience can be compared to the suggested approach using ANFIS, entropy weight, and NSPSO to model detailed responses and determine the optimal alternative. This optimization strategy works for numerous burnishing chores. Burnishing tools and fluid energy use harm the environment and machining costs. A more detailed analysis that considers sustainable performance can follow (Nguyen Trung Thanh et al., 2021).

Trung Thanh Nguyen et al. optimized MQL system parameters, such as nozzle diameter, impingement angle, air pressure, and flow rate, to reduce maximum profile peak height of roughness (MAR) and increase Vickers hardness (VH) for minimum quantity lubrication-based burnishing. ANN models for burnishing answers were proposed using optimal inputs. The Multi-objective glowworm swarm optimization (MOGSO) and VIKOR method determined appropriate burnishing settings and objectives. The ideal results were determined using RSM-desirability and compared to MOGSO-VIKOR. Following the authors, the greatest nozzle diameter and flow rate can reduce roughness peak height, while the intermediate impingement angle and air pressure are preferred. To increase Vickers hardness, use the highest nozzle diameter, flow rate, and air pressure, and use the middle impingement angle (Nguyen et al., 2022).

ANN models of burnishing performances benefit from all MQL system characteristics. The MAR model identifies flow rate as the most important element, followed by nozzle diameter, impingement angle, flow rate, and air pressure. In the VH model, flow rate is the most important factor, followed by air pressure, nozzle diameter, and impingement angle. The 4–10–2 ANN architecture efficiently reveals the relationship between MQL system variables, roughness peak height, and Vickers hardness. The ANN technique proposes considerable and appropriate

burnishing responses. The created models can accurately anticipate the response values of the minimum quantity lubrication-based burnishing operation of a hardened 50Cr steel (Nguyen et al., 2022).

Fig. 4.11. Structure of the ANN model (Nguyen et al., 2022)

MOGSO-VIKOR suggests appropriate optimal values for nozzle diameter, impingement angle, flow rate, and air pressure: 1.5 mm, 45 deg., 130 ml/h, and 0.6 MPa. VH increases by 14.0% and MAR decreases by 17.0% in the optimal solution. The MOGSO yields superior results compared to the standard MOPSO. The RSM-desirability strategy proved less effective than the ANN-MOGSO-VIKOR approach in solving the complex optimization problem (Nguyen et al., 2022).

4.4. Literature review on minimum quantity lubrication (MQL) technique.

Minimum quantity lubrication (MQL) commonly referred to as near-dry machining (NDM), involves the application of cutting fluids in extremely small quantities, typically around 0.01% of the volume utilized in flood-cooled milling. Like any other method in machining operations, the efficacy of this method is contingent upon the choice of cutting fluid, workpiece material, and machining process. While the use of high-pressure coolant is limited due to a lack of comprehensive understanding of the approach, the application of the Minimum Quantity Lubrication (MQL) technique is versatile and can be utilized in many machining processes, with varied workpiece materials and cutting tool materials. The majority of studies on the implementation of the high-

pressure coolant method have mostly focused on hard-to-cut materials (Sunday Albert Lawal et al., 2013).

Research by Sunday Albert Lawal et al., has demonstrated that the use of vegetable oil-based lubricants in machining processes, known as the MQL method, is the most effective solution for addressing the environmental issues associated with mineral oil-based lubricants. In addition to tackling environmental issues, experts have determined that the use of vegetable oil lubricant in the MQL process demonstrates superior machining capabilities. MQL also demonstrates cost savings because of decreased expenses associated with managing cutting fluids. Nevertheless, variables such as the material of the workpiece, the machining process, the material of the cutting tool, and the machining circumstances continue to be crucial factors in determining the effectiveness of the Minimum Quantity Lubrication (MQL) technique using vegetable oil lubricant (Sunday Albert Lawal et al., 2013).

5. The operation of the experiment

The design of the experiment is one of the vital parts of our research because it will be helpful enough to effectively support the theoretical assumptions and claims made in the literature review. During the design of the experiment, we will consider multiple factors that will influence our results. They are the workpiece composition, cutting parameters, machine power and capacity, tool geometry, measuring system, and machines. The average surface roughness (SR) and Vicker hardness (VH) of the roller burnishing operation are measured by applying the burnishing parameters, which consist of the spindle speed, feed rate, and depth of burnishing.

5.1. Application of minimum quantity lubrication (MQL) in the experiment.

We use an MQL system with a fog-type spray head: a method that uses a high-pressure gas flow mixed with a cooled lubricant and sprayed directly into the cutting area. Under the influence of high-pressure gas flows, a cold lubricant is formed in the form of fog. Use a cooled lubricant mixed with a high-pressure compressed air stream to form a fog to spray directly into the cutting area. Under the influence of high pressure, the cool lubricant is converted into countless tiny spherical particles. This increases the area of exposure of the cold lubricant and the cutting tool, machining details, and burr, resulting in the ability to load heat out of the cut area which is generated by the lubrication function – cooling to the maximum and minimizing the amount of cooled solution.

Fig. 5.1. MQL system with a fog-type spray head

Figure 5.1 describes the MQL system with 8 main components which are denoted from 1 to 8 respectively: Compressed air supply system (1), Pressure control system (2), Pulse generator (3), Lubricant container (4), Piston pumper (5), Fluid valve (spray valve) (6), tools (7) and workpiece (8).

Operating principles of the MQL system (as described in Figure 5.1): The air through the compressor is compressed at a pressure large enough through the pressure adjustment valve. The compression air will give the fixed pressure as desired. The air is put into the electromagnetic valve under the influence of the current, the valve passes through the air to the mixer. At the same time, the pump at the MQL container operates to push MQL lubricant through the filter part of the container into the frequency generator, then the output pressure of the lubricant is adjusted by the valve, and the solution continues to be delivered to the mixer. The mixture of air and lubricant is mixed and divided into two lines into two syringes for irrigation in the machining area.

Fig. 5.2. (a): The MQL system; (b): The MQL system was installed in the machine

5.2. Applying the Box-Behnken approach to the process of producing experimental results

The Box-Behnken method is an efficient approach to the design of the experiment. In this method, each element is assigned three levels: -1, 0, and 1. These levels represent the lowest, middle, and highest available ranges. On both the centre and the edge of the block, the design points are assigned by the designer. This strategy reduces the number of tests, which in turn leads to a reduction in both the expenses and the amount of human labour required. The following formula is used to determine the number of experiments (NE) in the Box-Behnken method (Le et al., 2023):

$$NE = 2k(k - 1) + C_p \quad (5.1)$$

Where k and C_p present the number of parameters and the number of centre points, respectively.

5 centre points are utilized in our experiment, and there are 3 levels of three process parameters (the spindle speed, feed rate, and depth of penetration); hence, 17 experiments are produced.

5.3. Surface Properties and Objectives

5.3.1. Objectives

Two parameters need to be measured: average surface roughness (SR) and Vicker hardness (VH).

Surface roughness (SR) is calculated according to the formula:

$$SR = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^3 R_{ai}}{3} \quad (5.2)$$

Where R_{ai} is the average roughness measured at one position after burnishing.

Vickers hardness (VH) is calculated according to the formula:

$$VH = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^3 VH_{ai}}{3} \quad (5.3)$$

Where VH_{ai} is the Vickers hardness at a position after rolling and burnishing.

5.3.2. Burnishing parameters

As we mentioned above, the input parameters consist of speed (S), feed rate (V_f), and depth of burnishing (D).

Table 5.1. The input burnishing parameter for the experiment.

Input technical parameter	Denote	Value 1	Value 2	Value 3
Spindle speed (RPM)	S	560	800	1120
Depth of burnishing (mm)	D	0.06	0.09	0.12
Feed rate (mm/min)	V_f	77	93	112

Values of different inputs are selected based on the characteristics of the tool machine used and the manufacturer's recommendations for the burnishing tool.

Therefore, the optimization problem is indicated as the maximization of surface hardness and minimization of surface roughness.

Conditions: $560 \leq S \leq 1120$ (RPM); $0.06 \leq D \leq 0.12$ (mm); $77 \leq V_f \leq 112$ (mm/min).

5.4. Experiment setup

The objective of the experiment is to determine the following parameters:

- Determine average surface roughness according to the cutting parameters of the burnishing tool after burnishing the inner cylindrical surface.
- Determines the impact of the roller burnishing head's cutting parameters on the hardness of the inner cylindrical surface after burnishing.

5.4.1. Workpieces

The objective is to assess the surface quality of the cylinder hole following processing by integrating MQL technology with other circumstances to optimize the technological parameters in the burnishing process.

The workpieces are composed of 40X high-strength alloy steel. The dimensions of the sample are as follows: 146 mm length inner diameter of 28 mm, and outside diameter of 40 mm. The hardness of the hole is measured at 470.4 HV, while the roughness Ra is recorded at 3.26 μm .

Table 5.2. The chemical properties of 40X high-strength alloy steel

Chemical properties	C	Si	Mn	P max	S max	Cr	Ni max	Cu max
	0,38- 0,43	0,15- 0,35	0,6- 0,85	0,03	0,03	0,9-1,2	0,25	0,3

5.4.2. Burnishing tool

Fig. 5.3. Burnishing tool

Table 5.3. Parameter of burnishing tool

Parameters	ΦA	Number of rollers	Adjustable range	Minimum adjustment range
	$28 \pm 0,2$ (mm)	6	0,5 (mm)	0,025 (mm)

5.4.3. Machine

Fig. 5.4. Milling machine FVHM-GS300A

We used a Milling machine, FVHM-GS300A, to carry out our experiment.

The specification of the Milling machine FVHM-GS300A is described in detail in the Appendix.

5.4.4. Carrying out the experiment

Install the elements of the MQL system on a metal plate. This metal plate is fixed to the desk with screws. Ensure that the MQL system is stable and robust during the rolling process. Supply the compressed air supply to the system through the air compressor, ensuring that the air input of the air compressor is relatively clean. The workpiece is positioned and fastened by a three-piece self-centered clamp. The burnishing tool is attached to the main axis of the machine. The straight movement of the burnishing tool is done with the support of the Z axis on the machinery.

Fig. 5.5. The experiment was conducting

5.5. Measurement

5.5.1. Surface roughness measurement metter

The surface roughness test of the sample after burnishing with the SJ-301 Mitutoyo surface roughness meter was conducted at the laboratory of the Department of Machine Design – Faculty of Mechanical Engineering – Le Quy Don University, Ha Noi, Viet Nam.

Fig. 5.6. SJ-301 Mitutoyo surface roughness meter

The specification of the Mitutoyo surface roughness meter is described in detail in the Appendix.

5.5.2. Micro hardness measurement machine

The Vicker hardness test of the sample after burnishing with the Wilson Wolpert Micro hardness measurement meter was conducted at the laboratory of the Department of Machine Design – Faculty of Mechanical Engineering – Le Quy Don University, Ha Noi, Viet Nam.

Fig. 5.7. Wilson Wolpert Micro hardness measurement meter

The specification of the Wilson Wolpert Micro hardness measurement meter is described in detail in the Appendix.

5.5.3. Conducting measurement

Fig. 5.8. Conducting measurement of surface roughness

Surface roughness is assessed by taking measurements at 3 distinct locations on the compacted rolling surface, following the ISO 4287 standard, with the Mitutoyo SurfTest-301 instrument. A standardized length of 4.0 mm is utilized for all machining models. The range that has been measured spans from 0.05 to 40 mm and a resolution of 0.01 mm is employed to improve the precision of the measurements.

Fig. 5.9. Conducting measurement of surface hardness

Surface hardness is determined by conducting Vickers hardness measurements at 3 distinct locations on a surface using a Wilson Wolpert testing machine. Each hardness test applies a pressure load of 29.42 N and maintains it for a duration of 10 seconds.

5.6. Experimental data for the roller burnishing process

After applying the Box-Behnken method to design experiments as performed in Section 5.2, 17 experiments are conducted, the result from the measurement is collected, and it is described in Table 5.4.

Table 5.4. Experimental data for the roller burnishing process

No.	S(RPM)	D(mm)	V_f (mm/min)	SR (μm)	VH (HV)
1	800	0.06	112	0.62	522.6
2	800	0.09	93	0.48	573.3
3	800	0.09	93	0.46	572.3
4	800	0.12	112	0.45	545.4
5	800	0.06	77	0.46	564.2
6	800	0.09	93	0.46	574.2
7	800	0.12	77	0.32	583.8
8	1120	0.09	112	0.38	546.8
9	800	0.09	93	0.45	574.1
10	1120	0.12	93	0.28	565.8
11	800	0.09	93	0.47	570.2
12	1120	0.09	77	0.31	576.9
13	560	0.12	93	0.58	531.2
14	560	0.09	112	0.68	514.4
15	1120	0.06	93	0.52	543.6
16	560	0.09	77	0.51	554.2
17	560	0.06	93	0.72	522.4

6. Develop an optimized model for the burnishing process

In this chapter, the basic concepts and application of Artificial neural networks to the project are presented. Along with that, the method to solve the multi-objective optimization problem is also presented, and the construction of the objective function is also formulated.

The project's prediction model and optimization model are programmed in Python on the GoogleColab platform and can be referenced at the following link:

<https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1pVyEXzHcSy-MOfm8sWsxRIERfPRTIFho?usp=sharing>

6.1. Develop a predictive model for the burnishing process

6.1.1. Artificial neuron network method

Recently, artificial intelligence has garnered significant attention across various scientific disciplines. The primary methods resulting from artificial intelligence research include the ANN approach, fuzzy logic, expert systems, and genetic algorithms. The ANN method is a commonly used methodology in various scientific domains for data processing and modelling. They are effectively utilized in various fields including learning, classification, generalization, optimization, and specification. Artificial neural networks (ANNs) are computational algorithms that are activated and operated within the nervous system using data. To comprehend how the artificial neural network operates, it is essential to analyze its structure as shown in Figure 6.1.

Fig. 6.1. Structure of ANN model

The picture illustrates that a neuron can have several inputs, each of which is multiplied by a weight. Weights dictate the impact of inputs on the cell. These products are added together and inputted into a transfer function to generate a result, which is then converted into an output. Various supplementary functions, transfer functions, and network structures can be utilized to apply this fundamental principle (Orkun Burak Öztürk, Ersan Başar, 2022).

Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) are versatile mathematical structures that can describe complex nonlinear relationships between different sets of input and output data. Artificial neural network (ANN) simulation models are valuable and efficient, particularly in situations when it is challenging to describe the characteristics of different activities using mathematical formulas (F. Rastegaripour et al., 2019).

Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) are capable of predicting the depth of scour through the creation of a multilayer, feed-forward network. An artificial neural network (ANN) begins with arbitrarily initialized connections between both input and output factors. The structure generally comprises three main layers of neurons: the input layer, hidden layers, and an output layer, where each neuron operates as an independent processing unit. The research employed a Python implementation of the artificial neural network (ANN) model, employing the PyTorch interface. PyTorch is an advanced machine learning and deep learning framework created by Facebook's artificial intelligence division. It is designed specifically for handling complex image analysis tasks, including object recognition, classification, and segmentation. It is not limited to these tasks and can be used alongside other tools to evaluate sophisticated algorithms. PyTorch provides a great platform for creating functions that can be automated in GPU settings (Waqed H. Hassan et al., 2022).

Artificial neural networks derive their power from the significant level of flexibility associated with their fundamental structures. Prior to deployment, the neural network undergoes training utilizing pre-existing datasets to construct a flexible network with input-output pairings dictated by the values of various connecting weights, centers, or biases included in the data. (M.H. Mohammed et al., 2021).

An artificial neural network (ANN) structure typically comprises three layers with lots of cells. Every individual cell within the input layer takes input data for each variable, performs a multiplication operation with the corresponding weight, and transmits the resulting values to the

corresponding cell within the hidden layer for the application of an activation function. The outputs are transmitted from the hidden layer to the output layer by the process of multiplying each element in the hidden layer by the weight of the corresponding connection to the output layer. The third layer produces the ultimate output information of the neural network for further data manipulation. The neural network's output could be examined to the actual output value to determine the proportion of variance. The outcome is considered reliable if the rate of error falls within a satisfactory range. To enhance the error rate, modify the interaction weights by starting at the final layer and progressing in the reverse direction. Continue this procedure until precise training is attained (Waqed H. Hassan et al., 2022).

6.1.2. Developing ANN model using Pytorch.

The study utilized Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) in PyTorch to develop a nonlinear simulation that, based on the training and testing data, predicts the depth of scour around the bridge pier.

PyTorch provides various beneficial classes that simplify tasks such as data augmentation and data parallelization via multi-threading and batching.

The ANN model was created on the Google Colab platform. The original data was inputted straight into the code.

The data distribution in the model was utilized for Artificial Neural Network (ANN) using the PyTorch framework, with a split of 70% for training and 30% for validation. 12 of 17 data sets (70%) have been used to train the artificial neural network, whereas 5 (30%) were employed to validate or assess the model's forecasts. The model is initialized using random values, which dictate the initial parameters, including depth of penetration (D), speed (S), and feed rate (V_f). These parameters have an influence on surface roughness (SR) and surface hardness (VH).

The project's ANN model includes three layers: the input layer (depth of penetration (D), speed (S), and feed rate (V_f)), the hidden layer, and the output layer (surface roughness (SR) and surface hardness (VH)).

The first layer is the input layer, which is initialized `self.fc1 = nn.Linear(input_size, hidden_size)`. An input layer, also called the input layer, takes in inputs to the network features. This layer applies a

linear transformation to the hidden layer. This layer is a big step that applies an addition bias to the weighted sum of the input features to prepare the data for further processing in the hidden layer. To apply non-linearity to this model, a function is applied and this step is through the hidden layer. The model uses a ReLU function to apply the required non-linearity process to the model: `relu1 = torch.nn.functional.relu(fc1)`. This function turns all the negative values to 0 while maintaining the positive values to the original ones. This function has the ability to handle Vanishing gradients and will make make the neurons learn and train well.

Lastly, the output layer is applied to the network through `self.fc2 = nn.Linear(hidden_size, output_size)`. This takes the processed data from the hidden layer and maps it to the final output, which is applied by taking the hidden layer's outputs into another linear transformation. For this model, the output is composed of two values, which are the surface roughness (SR) and surface hardness (VH).

The model is wrapped by the `SimpleNN` class which has the defined model's architecture. The `__init__` contains the initialization of the input-to-hidden and hidden-to-output linear transformations.

Fig. 6.2. Design of the ANN model-based PyTorch application was utilized in our research.

A function must be established for the model to evaluate the accuracy of its forecasts compared to the experimental values and make necessary adjustments. The mean square error (MSE) loss

function was utilized. Using the torch library, this is the sum of the squared discrepancies between the forecasted variable and target values. The “*torch.nn*” library provides various loss functions.

In addition to computing the loss, backpropagation is used to calculate the gradients of the trainable parameters. To reset all previously calculated gradients, the “*optimizer.zero_grad()*” method must be called after each use of the loss function. The number of epochs was set to 1500 initially, and the number of neurons of the hidden layer was set to 10. Training and test figures were plotted every 50 epochs to display the model's progress. Every 50 epochs, the code prints out the training and test losses to monitor the progress of the model's performance. This process ensures that the model is effectively trained and evaluated, providing insight into how well it is learning and generalizing to new data.

6.2. Develop an optimization model for the burnishing process

6.2.1. Multi-objective optimization problem and searching space

In the project, we aim to optimize multi-objectives, namely surface roughness and Vicker hardness. Specifically, we aim to determine a combination of 3 machining parameters that minimizes surface roughness and maximizes Vicker hardness.

Concerning the searching space, the spindle speed is limited to 3 specific values: 560 RPM, 800 RPM, and 1120 RPM. Similarly, the feed rate can only be set to 77 mm/min, 93 mm/min, and 112 mm/min. The reason is that we utilized the FVHM-GS300A milling machine, which is a conventional milling machine. We cannot personalize and modify the machining parameters, but we can only make adjustments based on predetermined parameters. The burnishing depth can be adjusted to a value between 0.06 mm and 0.12 mm.

6.2.2. Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) – an optimization method and the formulation of optimization objective function.

The described technique, also known as TOPSIS, which is the Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution, is one of the most promising algorithms in multi-objective optimization. It is widely used in selecting the best alternatives for different complex systems where a set of conflicting objectives is to be considered. One of the main aims of multi-objective optimization is to

find a set of solutions that will allow for obtaining the optimal trade-off between a number of objectives that can be conflicting.

The idea of the TOPSIS is to evaluate each alternative in relation to both the ideal solution and the worst case. The ideal solution presents the maximum performance level of the objective, and the worst case is an option within the lowest level of performance. For each alternative, the system computes the similarity to the ideal solution and the distance from the worst case. Then, according to these results, it can be identified which alternative is to be preferred because it is more similar to the ideal solutions and it is more remote from the worst case.

One of the advantages of TOPSIS is its straightforwardness and instinctive quality. The alternatives are ranked according to measures of how good they are in comparison with the optimal solution. At the same time, the system can be fed and interpreted very easily. Also, it ought to be said that TOPSIS has relevance in analyzing both quantitative and qualitative data, which makes the technique very useful and important in its applicability. It is a very strong and robust instrument that might offer valuable information to the people who facilitate making decisions in complicated choice situations.

The formulation of optimization objective function:

- Step 1: Determine the objectives: Identify the objectives pertinent to the multi-objective optimization problem and construct a matrix of different options based on their values, assigning weights to each objective.

In this project, two objectives are surface roughness and Vicker hardness. The "weight" coefficient of the two objectives is represented as equal since we have set the importance of the two objectives above to be equal.

- Step 2: Standardize the matrix: Standardize the matrix of choices by assigning values to each objective in order to establish a uniform scale for comparison. This can be accomplished by using the equation shown below:

$$\bar{X}_{mn} = w(n) * \left\{ \frac{X_{mn}}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n X_{mn}^2}} \right\} \quad (6.1)$$

Where \bar{X}_{mn} is the standardized value for the m^{th} alternative (combination of 3 machining parameters) and n^{th} objectives, and $w(n)$ is the chosen weight.

- Step 3: Determine the optimal solutions: The positive ideal solution reflects the best value for each criterion, while the negative ideal solution represents the lowest value. The solutions can be derived using the following formulas:

+ For maximization objective (the maximization of Vicker hardness objective):

Positive ideal solution:

$$(V^+) = \max(\bar{X}_{mn}) \quad (6.2)$$

Negative ideal solution:

$$(V^-) = \min(\bar{X}_{mn}) \quad (6.3)$$

+ For minimization objective (the maximization of Surface roughness objective):

Positive ideal solution:

$$(V^+) = \min(\bar{X}_{mn}) \quad (6.4)$$

Negative ideal solution:

$$(V^-) = \max(\bar{X}_{mn}) \quad (6.5)$$

- Step 4: Determine the distance: The following equations can be used to determine the distance of each alternative to the positive and negative ideal solutions using an appropriate distance measure, such as the Euclidean distance:

$$D_m^+ = \sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^k [X_{mn} - V_n^+]^2} \quad (6.6)$$

$$D_m^- = \sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^k [X_{mn} - V_n^-]^2} \quad (6.7)$$

Where D_m^+ and D_m^- are the distances of the m^{th} alternative (combination of 3 machining parameters) to the positive and negative ideal solutions.

- Step 5: Calculate the proximity in step five: By using the following equation, which is provided below, one can determine how close each option is to both the best and worst values:

$$C_m = \frac{D_m^-}{D_m^- + D_m^+} \quad (6.8)$$

Where C_m is the closeness index of the m^{th} alternative to the ideal solution.

- Step 6: rank the options: Put the options in order of closestness to the best option; the option with the highest closeness index is deemed the most advantageous.

7. Result and discussion

In this 7th chapter, Parametric influences of burnishing parameters on surface roughness and hardness are evaluated and analyzed. ANOVA is also used to evaluate and compare the influence of machining parameters on output parameters. The project's ANNs model is also evaluated for accuracy, and the results of multi-objective optimization parameters are presented.

7.1. Parametric influences of burnishing parameters on surface properties

Figures 7.1 to 7.6 depict the impact of machining factors such as spindle speed, feed rate, and burnishing depth on surface roughness and Vicker hardness. The graphs are generated from the data of 17 experiments. The blue column illustrates the actual values of roughness and hardness that were measured during the experiments. On the other hand, the orange line indicates the average values of roughness or hardness for each given machining mode.

Figure 7.1. The influence of spindle speed on surface roughness

Figure 7.1 demonstrates that the spindle speed (S) affects surface roughness (SR). When the speed increases from 560 to 800 RPM, the surface roughness decreases by a maximum of 55.5%. Increasing the speed from 800 RPM to 1200 RPM results in a slight decrease in the aspect ratio of surface roughness. Higher speeds lead to reduced hardness and strength of the workpiece due to increased temperatures. When the material is compressed more gently, its roughness decreases.

Figure 7.2. The influence of feed rate (V_f) on surface roughness

Figure 7.3. The influence of burnishing depth on surface roughness

Figure 7.2 illustrates that the surface roughness (SR) increases by roughly 57% maximum when the feed rate (V_f) is raised from 77 to 112 mm/min. This is demonstrated by the result: when the feed rate is low, the distance between burnishing routes decreases. This causes the tool-tip flat anomaly to decrease, which in turn leads to a reduction in roughness during the burnishing process. If you raise the feed rate, you will see that the feed marks between the burnishing traces get broader, which

will result in an increase in the surface roughness. The use of a low feed rate is recommended for the purpose of minimizing surface roughness. This is due to the fact that it improves the action of the burnishing tool and encourages constant metal flow.

With an increase in the burnishing depth (D) (from 0.06 to 0.12 mm), it is possible to assert that the surface roughness (SR) lowers (roughly around a maximum of 61%), as demonstrated in Figure 7.3. If the depth is increased, the burnishing pressure will be increased, and the material will be burnished relatively less. As a result of the valleys being filled in and the peaks being flattened, the roughness of the terrain is reduced.

Figure 7.4. The influence of spindle speed on Vicker Hardness

Figure 7.4 illustrates how the spindle speed influences the Vickers hardness of the material. It has been demonstrated through the findings that the value of Vickers hardness (VH) is increased when the spindle speed (S) is gradually increased. The reason for this is that when the speed of the spindle increases, the temperature in the area where the machining is taking place likewise boosts, which results in an increase in the amount of plastic deformation. The result is that an increase in spindle speed results in an increase in the Vicker hardness score.

Although it was not specified in the experiment, after the maximum point, the spindle speed continued to climb, but the stiffness gradually declined. This was the case even though the experiment did not mention it. Increased speeds result in an excessive increase in the press rolling

temperature at the machining zone. This allows for the relief of residual stress, which in turn leads to a decrease in the value of the VH component.

Figure 7.5 illustrates how the Vickers hardness is affected by the burnishing depth (D). As burnishing depth increases, the Vicker hardness (VH) value also increases correspondingly. Initially, the increase in burnishing depth results in hardness due to higher compression pressure, which leads to a rise in Vickers hardness value. After reaching the maximum point, each additional increase in pressing depth results in a tiny drop in hardness. As the rolling depth increases, the temperature in the rolling area can surpass the acceptable range, leading to a fall in residual stress and therefore a decrease in the VH value.

Figure 7.5. The influence of burnishing depth on Vicker hardness

Figure 7.6. The influence of Feed rate on Vicker hardness

As shown in Fig. 7.6, it can be stated that an increased higher V_f (from 77 to 112 mm/min) decreases the Vicker hardness. At a low feed rate, the number of burnishing traces increases, and the material is extensively treated; hence, higher hardness is obtained. A higher feed rate decreases the processing time; hence, the Vicker hardness decreases

Figures 7.7 to 7.9 illustrate the interaction effects that pairs of process inputs have on the surface roughness model.

Figure 7.7 shows how spindle speed (S) and burnishing depth (D) affect surface roughness (SR).

The figure shows that the roughness is lower when the spindle speed and burnishing depth are high. However, the roughness remains high if the spindle speed is small, regardless of the burnishing depth value.

Figure 7.8 shows how spindle speed (S) and feed rate (V_f) affect surface roughness (SR). The graphic shows that more spindle speed and less feed rate reduce roughness.

Figure 7.9 depicts the impact of feed rate (V_f) and burnishing depth (D) on surface roughness. The figure indicates that when the burnishing depth value is higher and the feed rate value is lower, the roughness value is higher.

Figure 7.7. The influence of spindle speed and burnishing depth on surface roughness

Figure 7.8. The influence of spindle speed and feed rate on surface roughness

Figure 7.9. The influence of burnishing depth and feed rate on surface roughness

Figures 7.10 to 7.12 illustrate the interaction effects that pairs of process inputs have on the Vicker hardness model.

Figure 7.10. The influence of burnishing depth and feed rate on Vicker hardness

Figure 7.10 illustrates a relationship between the burnishing depth (D), feed rate (V_f), and Vicker hardness (VH). It shows that when the burnishing depth grows and the feed rate drops, the Vicker hardness also increases.

Figure 7.11. The influence of spindle speed and feed rate on Vicker hardness

Figure 7.11 illustrates the impact of spindle speed (S) and feed rate (V_f) on Vicker hardness. This figure demonstrates that an increase in spindle speed and a decrease in feed rate result in higher values of Vickers hardness.

Figure 7.12. The influence of spindle speed and burnishing depth on Vicker hardness

Figure 7.12 illustrates the impact of spindle speed (S) and burnishing depth (D) on Vicker hardness (VH). According to Figure 7.12, there is a direct relationship between the spindle speed, feed rate, and the Vicker hardness value. As the spindle speed and feed rate increase, the Vickers hardness value also increases.

7.2. ANOVA of burnishing parameters on surface surface properties

Fig. 7.13. The influence of factors on Surface roughness

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) is utilized to evaluate the results of surface roughness and Vicker hardness of the burnishing process, with the aim of identifying the primary elements that influence

the performance metrics. Factors with a p-value less than 0.05 in the ANOVA table are deemed significant, whereas factors with a p-value more than 0.1 are considered irrelevant. Table 7.1 and Table 7.2 displayed the analysis of variance (ANOVA) results for surface roughness and Vicker hardness, respectively.

Table 7.1. ANOVA for surface roughness

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: Surface roughness

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Contribution (%)
Corrected Model	.237 ^a	12	.020	151.778	<.001	
Intercept	3.247	1	3.247	24977.576	<.001	
S	.125	1	.125	961.538	<.001	56
D	.060	1	.060	457.788	<.001	26
V _f	.035	1	.035	270.096	<.001	16
S * D	.003	1	.003	19.231	.012	1
S * V _f	.002	1	.002	19.231	.012	1
D * V _f	.000	1	.000	1.731	.259	0
S * D * V _f	.000	0	.	.	.	
Error	.001	4	.000			
Total	4.145	17				
Corrected Total	.237	16				

a. R Squared = .998 (Adjusted R Squared = .991)

According to the ANOVA table (Table 7.1), all spindle speeds, feed rates, and burnishing depth are the primary parameters that influence the surface roughness of the burnishing process. The factor that most affect surface roughness is spindle speed, with 56% of the contribution, followed by burnishing depth and feed rate, with 26% and 16% of the contribution, respectively. Since the p-values for the interaction between the feed rate and burnishing depth variable are 0.259, which is above 0.1, it can be concluded that the surface roughness was not influenced. Furthermore, it was

shown that the interaction between the spindle speed and burnishing depth, as well as the interaction between the spindle speed and feed rate, have slight impacts on the surface roughness of our burnishing process.

Table 7.2. ANOVA for Vicker hardness

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: Vicker Hardness

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Contribution
Corrected Model	7715.403 ^a	12	642.950	235.772	<.001	
Intercept	4183479.555	1	4183479.555	1534095.913	<.001	
S	1537.351	1	1537.351	563.752	<.001	30
D	673.445	1	673.445	246.955	<.001	13
V _f	2808.751	1	2808.751	1029.978	<.001	55
S * D	44.890	1	44.890	16.461	.015	1
S * V _f	23.522	1	23.522	8.626	.043	1
D * V _f	2.560	1	2.560	.939	.387	
S * D * V _f	.000	0	.	.	.	
Error	10.908	4	2.727			
Total	5244595.320	17				
Corrected Total	7726.311	16				

a. R Squared = .999 (Adjusted R Squared = .994)

Based on the ANOVA table (Table 7.2), it can be concluded that all spindle speeds, feed rates, and burnishing depth have a substantial effect on the Vicker hardness of the burnishing process. The primary determinant of Vicker hardness is the feed rate, which accounts for 55% of its overall impact. The spindle speed and burnishing depth contribute 30% and 13%, respectively. The Vicker hardness was not substantially affected by the interaction between the feed rate and burnishing depth variable, as indicated by their p-values of 0.387, which is greater than 0.1. Furthermore, the

study demonstrated that the interaction between the spindle speed and burnishing depth, as well as the interaction between the spindle speed and feed rate, have a slight impact on the Vicker hardness during the burnishing process.

Fig. 7.14. The influence of factors on Vicker hardness

7.3. Evaluating the Predictive Model

Learning curves are frequently used as a diagnostic tool in machine learning to evaluate algorithms that incrementally learn from a training dataset. The model's performance on both the training dataset and a separate validation dataset can be assessed after each training update. This process allows for the visualization of performance through learning curves. Examining the learning curves of models while training can help identify issues with learning, such as underfitting or overfitting, and assess if the training and validation datasets are adequately representative. Learning curves are often used in machine learning to assess algorithms as they progressively optimize their internal parameters., like deep learning neural networks.

Throughout the machine learning model training process, the model's status can be assessed at each iteration of the training algorithm. The model's performance can be assessed by evaluating it on the training dataset to gauge its learning progress. It can also be assessed using a hold-out validation dataset separate from the training dataset. Evaluating the validation dataset provides insight into the model's ability to generalize. Training Learning Curve is a curve derived from the training

dataset to assess the model's learning progress. Meanwhile, the Validation Learning Curve is a learning curve derived from a separate validation dataset to assess the model's generalization performance.

Analysing the shape and dynamics of a learning curve can help assess a machine learning model's behaviour and potentially recommend specific configuration adjustments to enhance learning and performance. Three frequent dynamics found in learning curves are Underfit, Overfit, and Good Fit.

Fig. 7.15. Train and Validation Learning Curves

According to Jason Brownlee, the learning algorithm aims to get a good fit, which lies between an overfit and underfit model. A good fit is characterized by a training and validation loss that declines and stabilizes with a minimal difference between the two final loss values. The model's loss is typically lower on the training dataset than on the validation dataset. Therefore, we should anticipate a difference between the train and validation loss curves. This gap is known as the "generalisation gap." A learning curve graphic indicates a good fit when the training loss lowers and stabilises and the validation loss plot lowers until it reaches a point of stability, showing a slight discrepancy with the training loss (Jason Brownlee, 2019).

Figure 7.15 demonstrates our Learning Curves of the ANN learning algorithm, which is plotted by the Pytorch framework. From this, we can easily see that our learning algorithm demonstrates an acceptable fit as the training loss plot decreases until it stabilizes, and the validation loss plot also decreases until it stabilizes, exhibiting a tiny deviation from the training loss.

In designing our predictive ANN model, we chose 5 experiments to test its accuracy. The ANN model's performance can be described in Table 7.3, Figure 7.16, and Figure 7.17. We can easily see that the difference between predictive results and experiment results is acceptable.

Table 7.3. The performance of the predictive ANN model

No.	Surface Roughness			Vicker Hardness		
	Experiment	ANN model	Error (%)	Experiment	ANN model	Error (%)
1	0.38	0.395	3,9	546.8	542.3	-0,82
2	0.32	0.3	-6,2	583.8	575.8	-1,37
3	0.68	0.71	4,4	514.4	510.76	-0,7
4	0.46	0.467	1,5	572.3	570.4	-0,33
5	0.45	0.427	-5,1	545.4	541.4	-0,73

Fig. 7.16. The comparison of predictive results and experiment results in terms of surface roughness.

Fig. 7.17. The comparison of predictive results and experiment results in terms of Vicker hardness.

Figure 7.18. Testing the adequacy of the ANN model of surface roughness

Figures 7.18 and 7.19 show regression graphs of predicted values of roughness and hardness compared to experimental values.

An R^2 -value of 0.9879 and 0.9938 indicates that the model explains approximately 98.79% and 99.38% of the variance in the dependent variable. This is a very high R^2 , suggesting that the model has an excellent fit for the data and is highly effective at predicting the forecasted variable based on the experimental variables included in the model.

Figure 7.19. Testing the adequacy of the ANN model of Vicker hardness

7.4. Optimization result

Fig. 7.20. Pareto chart representing the optimal point of surface roughness and Vicker hardness

Our research's optimisation model is constructed on the Google Colab platform utilising the TOPSIS approach and Python programming.

We aim to find the ideal machining parameters to provide the lowest surface roughness and highest Vicker hardness, as we previously stated. The "weight" coefficient of the two objectives is

represented as equal since we have set the importance of the two objectives above to be equal. By altering the above matrix, we can vary the weight of each aim based on our requirements.

After programming and execution are finished, TOPSIS provides accurate results. The optimal burnishing process parameters are a spindle speed of 1120 RPM, a feed rate of 77 mm/min, and a burnishing depth of 0.12 mm. With these parameters, we can determine the surface roughness and Vicker hardness values, 580.23 HV and 0.204 μm , respectively. The evaluation of the impact of burnishing parameters on the surface hardness and roughness provided in section 7.1 makes the results mentioned above entirely logical.

The Pareto chart of the problems optimal detects produced by TOPSIS is shown in Figure 7.20.

Table 7.4 displays the comparison of the pre-burnishing and burnishing surfaces. Consequently, the surface roughness is reduced by 93.74%, and the Vicker hardness is increased by 23.45% compared to the milled surface. The roller burnishing procedure effectively reduces surface roughness and enhances surface hardness. Applying burnishing pressure reduces the imperfections on the milled surface and fills in the valleys. Furthermore, this process facilitates the generation of plastic deformation, hence enhancing the hardness of the outermost layer. Put simply, the burnished surface greatly improves its surface qualities.

Table 7.4. The comparison of surface properties between burnishing and milling processes

Machining method	Mechanical properties	
	Surface roughness (μm)	Vicker hardness (HV)
Burnishing	0.204	580.23
Milling	3.26	470
Improvement	93.74%	23.45%

7.5. The validation test of the optimisation result

After achieving the optimal results, we conducted actual experiments to verify the roughness and hardness outcomes with the optimal machining parameters. Table 7.5 compares the differences between surface roughness and Vicker hardness results from actual experiments and those from the optimisation model.

Table 7.5. The validation test of the optimisation result

Machining parameters: - Spindle speed of 1120 RPM - Feed rate of 77 mm/min - Burnishing depth of 0.12 mm	Mechanical properties	
	Surface roughness (μm)	Vicker hardness (HV)
Validation experiment	0.21	582.2
Optimisation model	0.204	580.23
Differences	2.85%	0.33%

8. Summary

This project comprehensively analyzes the burnishing process by examining the effect of the burnishing parameters on the surface qualities. It also investigates using Artificial Intelligence to optimize the burnishing process better.

Experiments are conducted on a Milling machine FVHM-GS300A, using the minimum quantity lubrication technique. The workpiece is made of high-strength 40X alloy steel, and the inner cylindrical surface of the workpieces was machined. The Box-Behnken approach is applied in experimental design to minimize the number of the conducted experiments, thereby minimizing the cost of the experimental process.

The purpose of this project is to use Artificial Neural Networks and the TOPSIS method to develop an optimization framework that is highly efficient and effective. The Artificial Neural Networks are incorporated into the optimization model for the purpose of predicting the characteristics of the surface. Input factors such as spindle speed, feed rate, tool burnishing depth, and the value of average surface roughness and Vicker hardness from the experiments are used for predicting the surface hardness and surface roughness. The TOPSIS technique is applied to evaluate the different solutions provided by the ANN in consideration of finding the burnishing parameters, which maximized the surface hardness and minimized the surface roughness in parallel. The following are hence the results it provided:

1. To enhance the Vicker hardness and minimize surface roughness, higher speed, and depth were utilized, while a lower feed rate was advised.
2. The spindle was determined to be the most efficient input for the roughness model, with the burnishing depth and feed rate following closely behind. The feed rate was determined to be the most influential factor in the Vicker hardness model, followed by the spindle speed and burnishing depth.
3. The optimal burnishing process parameters are a spindle speed of 1120 (RPM), a feed rate of 77(mm/min), and a burnishing depth of 0.12(mm). Using these metrics, we can determine the surface roughness and Vicker hardness values, which are 580.23 HV and 0.204 μm , respectively.

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APPENDIX

- Specification of Milling machine FVHM-GS300A

SPECIFICATION		UNIT: mm	
TABLE	TABLE SIZE	1270x300 (1470x300 OPT.)	
	T SLOT (WxNO.xPITCH)	16x3x80	
TRAVEL	XxYxZ-MANUAL	930x390x450	
	XxYxZ-AUTO	920x370x450	
FEED	LONG./MIN	18-320(6 STEPS) (50 Hz) 22-384(6 STEPS) (60 Hz)	
	LONG. RAPID TRAVERSE/MIN	1040 (50 HZ) 1250 (60 HZ)	
	CROSS/MIN	50-2200 VARI. (50/60 HZ)	
	VERTICAL/MIN	360 (50 HZ) 430 (60 HZ)	
VERTICAL SPINDLE	SPINDLE NOSE	N.S.T 40	
	TEPS	16	INVERTER VARI.
	SPINDLE SPEED RPM	62-3000 (50 Hz) 75-3600 (60 Hz)	60-3600 (50/60 Hz)
	SWIVELLING ANGLE	45° (R&L)	
	QUILL TRAVEL	140	

	QUILL FEEDS/REV	0.035/0.07/0.14
	SPINDLE NOSE TO TABLE	85-535
	SPINDLE CENTER TO COLUMN	190-690
	CROSS TRAVEL OF RAM	500
HORIZONTAL SPINDLE	SPINDLE NOSE	N.S.T 40
	SPINDLE SPEED RPM	60-1440 (50 Hz) 75-1730 (60 Hz)
	STEPS	9
	SPINDLE TO BOTTOM OF RAM	173
	SPINDLE CENTER TO TABLE	0-450
MOTOR	VERTICAL SPINDLE	5HP – 2P/4P
	HORIZONTAL SPINDLE	5HP – 4P
	TABLE FEED X AXES	3/4 HP – 4P
	TABLE FEED Y AXES	1/2 HP – 4P – 1/5
	TABLE RAPID Z AXIS	1/4 HP – 4P
	COOLANT PUMP	1/8HP – 2P
SIZE	MACHINE (LxWxH)	1740x1615x2400
	NET WEIGHT (Kgs)	2350

- Specification of SJ-301 Mitutoyo surface roughness meter

INCH-METRIC:	METRIC
CABLE LENGTH:	1 M
DETECTOR MEASURING FORCE:	0.75 MN
STYLUS TIP ANGLE:	60°
STYLUS TIP RADIUS:	2 μm
MEASURING METHOD:	INDUCTION METHOD
STYLUS:	DIAMOND TIP
SKID RADIUS:	40 mm
MEASURING FORCE:	0.75 mn
INTERFACE:	RS-232 C INTERFACE FOR INPUT/OUTPUT, DIGIMATIC OUTPUT, COMPACT FLASH CARD
PROFILES:	PRIMARY PROFILE (P), ROUGHNESS PROFILE (R), DIN 4,776, MOTIF
DISPLAY RANGE:	RA, RQ: 0.01 μm - 100 μm RY, RZ, RT, RV, R3Z, RK, RPK, RVK, R, RP, RX, AR, W, WX, WTE: 0.02 μm - 350 μm S, SM: 2 μm - 4,000 μm HSC, PC: 2.5/CM - 5,000/CM;

	PPI: 6.35 - 12,700/INCH DC: - 350 μm - + 350 μm LO: 0.1 MM - 99,999 MM MR, MR 1, MR 2: 0 - 100 % A1, A2: 0 - 15,000
ROUGHNESS STANDARD:	DIN, ISO, ANSI, JIS
SAMPLING LENGTH (L):	0.08 MM, 0.25 MM, 0.8 MM, 2.5 MM, 8 MM OR INPUT
NO. OF SAMPLING LENGTH (L):	X 1, X 3, X 5, X L* (* = OU N'IMPORTE QUELLE VALEUR)
DIGITAL FILTER:	2RC-75%, 2RC-75% (PHASE CORRECTED), GAUSS -50%
CUT-OFF LENGTH:	LC: 0.08 mm, 0.25 mm, 0.8 mm, 2.5 mm, 8 MM, LS: 2.5 μm , 8 μm , 25 μm
PRINTER:	THERMAL PRINTER (PRINTING WIDTH: 48 MM)
STATISTICS:	MAX/MIN, AVERAGE VALUE, STANDARD DEVIATION (S), PASS RATIO, FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION TABLE
AUTO-SLEEP:	AUTOMATIC AFTER 5 MINUTES
TOLERANCE:	UPPER/LOWER LIMIT VALUES FOR THREE PARAMETERS
MASS:	1.7 kg

- Specification of Wilson Wolpert Micro hardness measurement meter

MANUFACTURER	WILSON WOLPERT.
HARDNESS SCALE	HV, HK
MAIN LOAD	0.3, 0.5, 1, 3, 5, 10, 20, 30KGF
HARDNESS MEASUREMENT STANDARDS	ISO 6507, ASTM E384 & E92, JIS Z2244
HOLD TIME	5-99 S
SIMPLIFICATION	0.5 M
MAGNIFICATION	100X, 200X
MEASUREMENT RESOLUTION	100X:800M; 200X:400M
VERTICAL TEST LIMIT	210MM
HORIZONTAL TEST LIMIT	160MM
OPERATING TEMPERATURE	10 – 38°C
SIZE	566 X300 X 710MM
WEIGHT	55KG
POWER SUPPLY	110-220V AC, 60/50HZ.

Acceptance Statement

Master thesis title: Developing advanced optimisation models for burnishing process

Student's name: Nguyen Thanh Tuan

Student's Neptun code: P8317F

Supervisor's name and position: Jacsó Ádám, Senior Lecturer

Supervisor's e-mail address: jacso.adam@gpk.bme.hu

The master thesis mentioned above is fully compliant with all the content and formal requirements required by the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering of the Budapest University of Technology and Economics for the Diploma and Thesis assignments.

I consider this thesis to be suitable for review and public defence.

Date of administration: 22nd of May, 2024

Supervisor

Dr. Jacsó Ádám